

Enhanced engagement strategy

MATS Deliverable 6.2

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Summary

The objective of the MATS project is to make a meaningful contribution to improving the design and framing of trade policy both at national (with a key focus on EU and Africa) and global levels with a view of achieving the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals). Acknowledging that trade policy implementation eventually occurs at national and regional level, evidence-based policy development, civil society and stakeholder dialogue play a significant role throughout the lifetime of the project. This enhanced engagement strategy (D6.2) is the second update on the envisaged engagement with stakeholders since the start of the project. It builds on the results of the Information Needs Assessment (D6.1), ongoing discussions on the design of the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub (D6.3) and the preparations of the stakeholder-civil society-policy dialogues (D6.4). The enhanced engagement strategy covers the following elements:

- i. Engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and actors
- ii. Structured feedback loops with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), case study partners and policymakers involved in the project.
- iii. Targeting of project outputs to current discourses, relevant organisations and policy processes
- iv. Using the most effective dissemination activities and forms.
- v. Monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities.

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Authors: Antonis Koukourikos, Bodo Steiner, Jonathan Matthysen, Karlheinz Knickel, Mari Carlson, María Bustamante, Pablo Vidueira, Panagiotis Zervas, Thierry Kesteloot

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Introduction

MATS aims to identify key leverage points that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being. The project aims to augment previous studies by expanding the range and depth of investigation through a mixed-methods analysis and participatory engagement with policymakers, civil society, and the wider stakeholder community. To maximise its impact, MATS initiates and contributes to policy dialogues, participates in relevant fora, and provides cutting-edge information to decision-makers in private and public sectors.

Working package (WP) 6 is dedicated to dialogue, dissemination, and exploitation, and leads the activities that are to contribute to an enhanced civil society–stakeholder–policy dialogue. The main goal is to foster effective interaction between researchers, policymakers, CSOs and the wider stakeholder community. It promotes early and continuing engagement with relevant stakeholders (see contact list, annex

3) and describes the interaction with relevant actors, particularly utilizing an evidence-based communication platform – the Sustainable Trade Hub (D6.3) – and a suite of communication activities (D6.5). This engagement strategy is based on the common experience that improved analyses and data are of little use if they do not effectively support more evidence-based decision-making and policy development.

MATS aims at obtaining maximum benefit from effective engagement and interaction between researchers, policymakers, civil society organizations (CSOs) and the wider stakeholder community. Throughout the project, a

Definition of 'actors' and 'stakeholders'

1. 'Actors' are individuals, organizations or institutions that operate within our object of study, being the agricultural trade regimes and policies at the private sector, national, EU, African and global levels.
2. 'Stakeholders' are those actors that potentially have an interest in and thus a stake in our project's output. A limited amount of actors are thus stakeholders, but all stakeholders are actors.

For more information, see '*Further engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and actors*'.

range of **discursive methods and tools** is used to foster collaboration. The project's '**Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub**' is being developed during MATS to contribute to more informed exchanges and consultations. It aims to serve primarily as an online repository of resources and as a place where stakeholders and researchers can engage with the materials and with the consortium members.

The deliverables in WP6 are:

- Information Needs Assessment (D6.1)
- Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (D6.2)
- Interactive communication platform 'Sustainable Trade Hub' (D6.3)
- Suite of workshops, communication toolkit and dissemination materials in support of an enhanced civil society and policy dialogue (D6.4, D6.5, D7.3)

Components of the Engagement Strategy

Evidence-based policy development and civil society and stakeholder dialogue play an important role throughout the lifetime of the project. This is vital for the success of the project: 1) the 15 Case Studies (CSs) collect evidence-based data at different levels (local, national, regional, global) of trade regimes which requires stakeholder engagement in the local environment, 2) MATS aims to connect the evidence-based information acquired in case studies with macro level policies by applying macro level modelling such as CGE modelling, and find impact pathways and key leverage points for change. Thus, engagement and interaction with all key stakeholders operating in the agri-food trade policy “sphere” needs to be taken into account. Furthermore, the final project results need to reach relevant policymakers and other relevant stakeholders. This poses challenges as the range of actors in the field is vast, but we aim to find a balance in the process of identifying relevant stakeholders. The authors note that the engagement process is continuously evolving, meaning more stakeholders can emerge as the project proceeds.

The enhanced engagement strategy covers the following elements:

- i. Engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and actors
- ii. Structured feedback loops with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), case study partners and policymakers involved in the project.
- iii. Targeting of project outputs to current discourses, relevant organisations and policy processes
- iv. Using the most effective dissemination activities and forms.
- v. Monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities.

Engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and actors

Information Needs Assessment (D6.1)

The enhanced engagement strategy was initially elaborated based on the results of the Information Needs Assessment (D6.1) carried out in M6 (December 2021) and in consultation with consortium members in Task 6.4 (*Coordinate the implementation of all engagement and dissemination activities*). The enhanced engagement strategy was updated in March 2022 (M10) and in May 2023 (M22). We will continue to adapt and improve this strategy when changes in context and opportunities require us to do so and at least once a year.

The Information Needs Assessment built on initial contacts of more than 100 relevant actors of networks of different project partners, including SEATINI, TNI, OSOL, NWU, ESRF, CRPA, KE, AUA and UM (please see the complete name list of the project partners in Annex 1). Since then, different actors and stakeholders have crossed the path of the MATS consortium which were added to the list (see Annex 3).

The initial list of potentially relevant actors included Academics, Agricultural Workers, Consumers associations, Farmers/Farmers Associations, Financial institutions, Government/Policy makers, Multilateral/International organisations, Non-Governmental Organisations, other Private Sector, Technical experts, and Traders. The actors who responded the survey of D6.1, identified themselves as research or academy (42%), followed by technical experts (19%) and nongovernmental organizations (19%). It is worth mentioning that actors directly involved in value chain activities – such as farmers, consumers, agricultural workers, traders, and other private sectors – had a lower presence. It was noted that this first consultation with potentially relevant actors' points to the need to broaden the MATS network so that a greater diversity of perspectives on agri-food trade are covered. In further activities attention therefore will be paid to the groups less represented so far, especially farmers, private sectors, women. Also, geographical representation will be enhanced to cover more stakeholders and actors from Africa, and therefore workshops and seminars will be held in Africa (e.g. Tanzania, October 23-27, 2023), and active efforts will be made through the

Figure 1. Field of work of respondents (respondents were able to pick multiple options)

African consortium partners to more effectively engage actors and actors in hybrid events in Europe (e.g., Zoom seminars, workshops and high-level policy meeting). Most of the respondents in the survey in D6.1 (65%) found their work relevant to MATS. Clustering the fields of work into three groups – see Figure 1 – reveal the linkages between broader fields such as agri-food trade and food systems transformation, with the enabling conditions for agri-food trade and the expected outcomes and sustainability impacts. Thus, actors whose work corresponds to food security and nutrition are usually also working on policies and governance, agri-food trade, or food systems transformation. The same happens with environmental sustainability and human well-being.

The geographical scope of the respondents' work covers Europe, Africa, the Americas, and Asia, and its distribution largely reflects the location of MATS partners and case studies.

Further engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and actors

For the purpose of this project, we differentiate between ‘stakeholders’ and ‘actors’. We also make a division on the basis of the mode of communication towards these two groups, being ‘engagement’ and ‘interaction’. These concepts are defined below.

The division between these groups as well as our communication strategy towards these groups is based on the concept of circle of control which consists of three concentric circles (see Figure 2):

- Our **circle of concern** contains all actors that operate within our object of study, which is the agricultural trade regimes and policies at the private sector, national, EU, African and global levels (see Grant Agreement 1.1 The project summary). Obviously, this is very wide and entails countless individuals which we will not be able to reach.
- Our **circle of influence** in contrast, contains actors from our circle of concern that we theoretically are able to reach and on which we can have an influence on with our communication and dissemination activities.
- Our **circle of control** consists of partners of the MATS project (see annex 1).

Figure 2. MATS partners, stakeholders and actors in circle of control, influence or concern

This gives us the background to define the four concepts:

1. 'Actors' are individuals, organizations or institutions that operate within our object of study, being the agricultural trade regimes and policies at the private sector, national, EU, African and global levels.
2. 'Stakeholders' are those actors that potentially have an interest in and thus a stake in our project's output. A limited amount of actors are thus stakeholders, but all stakeholders are actors.
3. 'Engagement' means the intentional targeting of (a group of) stakeholders with the goal of making them aware of the projects' output.
4. 'Interaction' means the intentional process of trying to establish a reciprocal involvement of (a group of) stakeholder in the MATS project's work and output. This means the stakeholder influences the outputs too. A limited amount of engagement leads to interaction, but all interaction is also engagement.

Because of our resource constraints, we focus our engagement and interaction activities on key leverage points and key leverage actors that (1) have an interest in and thus a stake in our output and (2) that we can engage and interact with through a reasonable and efficient investment of our resources (i.e. circle of influence). The groups of actors that fulfill both these conditions are our target groups (see Table 1). Depending on the return of investment, we will seek to engage with some stakeholders, and interact with others.

	Circle of influence	Circle of concern
Actors	No targets	No targets
Stakeholders	Target groups	No targets

Table 1. Conditions for being considered within MATS's target groups

- i. The first target group are **policymakers, civil society organizations (CSOs), farmers organizations, and private sector** representatives actively involved in promoting and implementing (sustainable) agriculture trade at local, regional, national, EU, and international levels.
- ii. The second target group are members of the **academic community** involved in scientific research on the linkages between agricultural trade, investment, environmental sustainability, and human well-being. This group also includes other **research projects** examining international

agri-food trade and sustainability and external experts not strictly belonging to the academic community (for example consultancy firms and research institutions)

- iii. The third target group are the **potential beneficiaries** of the policies and initiatives promoting sustainable trade. This will include the wider community including actors in food value chains, as well as consumer-citizens that are dependent on trade for the provision of agri-food products.

Engagement and interaction with each of the target groups described above offer specific opportunities and pose distinct challenges. This requires a specific engagement strategy for these target groups. The broad lines of this strategy are described in the table below. It is further operationalised in the following chapter.

	Opportunities	Challenges	Strategy
Group I policymakers, CSOs, farmer organizations, and private sector representatives	This group may have more leverage than others in transforming trade regimes, given their unique position within it.	This group is difficult to access given their elite position (specifically policy makers) and require specific technical language to be engaged.	We make adapted products with specific language and content that cater to the needs of this group.
Group II Academics and the scientific community	This group has expertise in research and scientific analysis and can help in adding scientific value for our research.	This group will naturally interact with the academic outputs of our study but are more difficult to mobilise for engagement with group I and group III.	We make use of existing networks, and create platforms for academics to engage with our materials and interact with actors from group I.
Group III potential beneficiaries	This group includes the ultimate potential beneficiaries of	This group is equally difficult to access given their marginal position	We aim to engage directly with group III through field work and engage

	our work, and must thus be adapted to the needs of that group.	(especially farmers in the Global South) and their heterogeneity.	with the larger public through media materials in accessible language.
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Table 2. Opportunities, challenges and strategies per target group

The outreach to stakeholders will be further enhanced in an incremental way through the following steps:

- i. Further engage with the respondents to the information needs assessment (D6.1)
- ii. Incremental enrichment of the database including relevant stakeholders interacted with in the WP3 (15 case studies), policymakers responsible for the institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks (WP4), and engaged in trade and sustainable development policy debates, as well as the wider community of civil society organizations (CSOs), and private actors (See Annex 3).
- iii. Linking with broader audiences through webinars (WP1-WP3-WP5)
- iv. Engagement and in person interaction with stakeholders through participation in relevant events and bilateral dialogue, the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub (T6.2), Twitter and LinkedIn (see the following chapter).
- v. Call WP leads and Project Advisory Group (PAG) members to further enrich stakeholders list as relevant for the project.

Structured feedback loops with CSOs, case study partners and policymakers involved in the project

The Information Needs Assessment showed initial stakeholders' interest in MATS, in improving the understanding of the interactions between agri-food trade, sustainability, and human well-being, and in the design of transition pathways toward sustainable agri-food trade. Along the continuously evolving stakeholder and actors' outreach, this understanding has strengthened. Stakeholders see potential value in the mixed-methods approach and, in the inclusion of case studies taking place in different continents.

The main ways of interaction identified in 6.1 were

1. the dissemination of the results of case studies (WP3) on the interactions between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being
2. the dissemination of discussion papers and policy briefs related to the design of transition pathways towards sustainable agri-food trade (WP5),
3. practical guides to improve agri-food trade practices towards sustainability (case study briefs WP3 and deliverables WP4 and WP5), and
4. the Sustainable Trade Hub (WP6) for joint work and discussions.

Drawing from the input of 6.1 and lessons learned during the implementation of other deliverables, MATS aims at enhancing this engagement through the following main elements:

- i. (Interim) results of WP1-WP5 feed into **high-level policy dialogues** in Africa and Europe with consortium members and external experts representing research, policy making, value chains actors and civil society.
- ii. **Webinars** and **online workshops** to collect CSOs and policy feedback to case study surveys, research questions and processes (WP6); and (online or in person) activities (press briefs, workshop meetings, material distribution at conference events) at national level to disseminate research results, feed relevant debates and discuss recommendations, related to the different case studies (WP3).

- iii. Transition pathways towards sustainable trade, and practices and policy-oriented outputs generated by MATS are subject to a thorough process of engagement, validation, and fine-tuning, based upon **peer-review** by consortium members, external experts, and stakeholders ensuring a diversity of perspectives and cross-fertilisation of views (WP5).
- iv. Bridging the gaps between knowledge, improved civil society and stakeholder dialogue, and more evidence-based policies through **customised dissemination tools** adapted to the needs of users.
- v. All consortium partners seek **active connections with relevant networks** and organisations, with a special focus to connect to policymakers, decision-makers in the private sector, civil society organizations, and practitioners in European and African countries and regions.
- vi. Engagement through the **Sustainable Trade Hub** D6.3.

Table 3 summarises the main activities and tools proposed for implementing the Engagement Strategy.

I. Policymakers, farmers organizations, private sector representatives, and CSOs (first target group)	
	Database of 15 case studies – covering a large variety of sectors, markets, food supply chains (FSCs) and contexts. This database can be referenced in adapted materials (policy briefs, papers, and reports, as well as media materials) targeting policymakers, farmers organizations, private sector representatives and CSOs and thus contribute to science-based advisory and advocacy activities.
	Sustainable Trade Hub with all outcomes and knowledge (data, discussion papers, policy briefs, scientific publications, videos, research and innovation protocols etc.) generated in the project. This will be the central place to which we reference when there is interest for further engagement from the target group. We will also reference this platform in our social media outreach.
	Policy briefs, papers, and reports – based on results and knowledge created in the case studies or WP4 and WP5, and when relevant co-created with public and private sectors decision-makers and civil society dialogue at different workshops. These papers are (1) used by consortium partners to disseminate the generated knowledge more broadly (Sustainable Trade Hub,

	social media.) (2) and to directly target policymakers and private sector representatives during advocacy and advisory activities.
	(Online) seminars, workshops, and events – webinars, workshops and events reflect on the current state of play of trade regimes to inform our work, as well as the application of our output in the policy process and aim to stimulate interaction between policymakers, farmers’ organizations, private sector representatives and CSOs.
	Media materials – For a selection of outputs from the MATS project we create press statements, write op-eds or propose to media outlets (websites, newsletters, magazines, newspapers) to publish our output. By sharing successful stories or problematic issues relating to case studies’ object of study. In that way, we inform the general public of negative or positive effects of specific trade regimes and proposed changes. Indirectly, we reach out to policymakers, farmers’ organizations, private sector representatives and CSOs in this way. This indirect reach may be reinforced by using specialist policy media outlets like for example Politico or Euractiv.
	High-level policy dialogues – MATS organises two international events (Africa and Europe) to interact on our projects’ topic, and bring policymakers, CSOs and scientists together in facilitated sessions. We aim to have direct engagement with policy makers (from governments or parliaments) and experts who hold key roles in shaping trade (for example from certification organizations), hence ‘policy dialogues’. The idea is indeed to inform both the work of our guests (policy makers and experts) as well as to inform the further work of the consortium. ‘High-level’ refers to the idea that we will zoom-out or break-out from day-to-day consortium operations and look at the bigger picture of agricultural trade and issues linked to it.
	Social media materials – Via the MATS social media accounts on LinkedIn and Twitter, we aim to boost the visibility of the outputs of our consortium as well as redirect internet traffic to the Sustainable Trade Hub. While not a precision tool, social media can be used to reach the specific target group.
II. Academic and scientific community (second target group)	
	Database of 15 case studies – covering a large variety of sectors, markets, food supply chains (FSCs) and contexts. This database will be a primary repository for academics and the scientific community to access our materials.
	Peer-reviewed publications – MATS showcases new concepts, pathways, regime and governance through theoretically driven analysis at academic events and in at least 8 international scientific journal articles.
	Sustainable Trade Hub – as above.
	Sustainable trade toolbox – frameworks, indicators and tools for a systemic analysis and assessment of the linkages between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being.
	High-level policy dialogues – as above.

	(Online) seminars, workshops and events – webinars, workshops and events reflect on the current state of play of trade regimes to inform our work and stimulate interaction between academics and the wider scientific community, as well as between this group and stakeholders from the first target group.
	Social media materials – as above.
III.	Potential beneficiaries (third target group)
	(Online) seminars, workshops and events – webinars, workshops and events reflect on the current state of play of trade regimes to collect input from potential beneficiaries (primarily through the execution of case studies) and discuss with them the result.
	Case study briefs – showcasing output from empirical analyses and the related discussions, to be shared with the stakeholders involved in the case studies as well as with the larger public through our Sustainable Trade Hub. These briefs are informed by the interaction with potential beneficiaries during (and after) the execution of the case studies.
	Media materials – For a selection of outputs from the MATS project we create press statements, write op-eds or propose to media outlets (websites, newsletters, magazines, newspapers) to publish our output. By sharing successful stories or problematic issues relating to case studies’ object of study. In that way, we inform the general public of negative or positive effects of specific trade regimes and proposed changes. Indirectly, we reach out to our potential beneficiaries (consumer-citizens, farmers) in this way.
	Sustainable Trade Hub – as above.
	Social media materials – as above.

Table 3. Tools and uses, by target group

Below is a visual overview of the table 3. It displays how the different dissemination tools (red), of which some are deliverables (green) described above provide input for one another (dotted lines). For example, the database of 15 case studies provides input to make policy briefs, papers and reports. These tools are used to engage or interact (solid lines) with our different target groups (yellow). The line describes briefly what the interaction entails.

Figure 3. Overview of how dissemination tools (red) of which some are deliverables (green) are used as input to each other (dotted lines) and to engage and interact (solid lines) with our target groups (yellow).

Targeting of project outputs to current discourses, relevant organisations, and policy processes

The connections between trade and sustainable development have risen to the very heart of trade policy discussion at national level, in the EU but also at varying levels in multilateral fora. This implies that our engagement strategy should target, where possible, the existing discussions and processes nationally, in Europe and Africa, and multilaterally. Our activities cover direct interaction with (throughout the project), communication activities (D6.5) and targeted dialogues with relevant stakeholders (D6.4) and actors.

Nationally, these processes are carried out towards respective ministries, relevant NGOs, and CSOs.

In the EU, the European Commission (DG TRADE, DG AGRI, DG INTPA, and others) and the European Parliament (MEPs in Committees such as ENVI, TRADE, and AGRI). We also include EU level NGOs, CSOs, and organizations representing farmers and agri-food traders.

At global level, MATS aims to contribute to peer reviewed expert processes, including those connected with the work of the High-Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) on Food Security and Nutrition (CFS), and IISD, through workshops and seminars. All these processes provide opportunities for external comments and contributions by MATS partners.

Food system transformation is high on the regional and international agendas, and different stakeholder networks are mobilising around related policy processes. They include:

- i. The discussions connected with the EU Green Deal and its policy packages such as Farm to Fork, Fit for 55, Biodiversity or trade strategies: They are the most elaborated EU response to achieving the SDGs. What their external impacts are and how trade rules need to be adapted to these new policy commitments remains unclear, and the MATS project aims to contribute to enhancing these discussions.

- ii. The new narrative on food systems put forward, including during the UN Food Systems Summit or at the CFS. The systemic approach gives more attention to sustainability and governance issues. The new dimension of agency of food security refers to the capacity of individuals or groups, the most vulnerable groups of society, to make decisions on food systems. Their engagement in policy processes shaping future food systems needs to be integrated in our engagement strategy.
- iii. The unilateralism and regional approaches in the countries' agendas are becoming more prominent. The role of international trade is more critically debated than ever, given the ongoing food and climate crises, pandemic and conflicts increasing hunger and inequalities.
- iv. Standards at various levels are being intensively discussed, with numerous initiatives: Public standards such as the legislative initiative by the European Commission: Sustainable Corporate Due Diligence, review of the Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) chapters in the Free Trade Agreements, ETS revision including the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), due diligence and deforestation-free supply chains, revision of pesticide import tolerances; Public-private standards developed in multistakeholder initiatives, for example the Coalitions emerging from the UN Food Systems Summit or the Living Income Community of Practice. Private standards and specific commodity standards are evolving, for instance those for soybeans, palm oil or cocoa.

As part of the analysis of the linkages (WP3) and the institutional frameworks (WP4), further engagement with the stakeholders' networks will be developed. This will lead to the participatory design of transition pathways (WP 5) along the following two steps:

- i. **Step 1:** Visioning process involving stakeholders primarily from the case studies to identify communalities and derive a joint MATS vision to formulation a vision of equitable economic partnerships in agricultural trade in support of a more sustainable, resilient food system (time horizon 2035+). In this process, all involved parties are invited to contribute through interviews, online surveys, and workshops.

- ii. **Step 2:** Formulation of transition pathways based on a participatory back casting process (WP5). This process builds on the results of Task 4.1 in WP4 and T5.1 in WP5 and identifies the required changes, incl. for local, regional, national, and European authorities. More contextualised pathways are elaborated through WP4 and 5, illustrating desired futures and elaborating the concrete steps necessary to reach them.

The linkages between MATS and relevant policy processes on agricultural trade and sustainable development **will be incrementally developed** by

- 1) identifying involvement of case studies partners in policy processes at national, regional or international levels (WP3),
- 2) exploring the relevant institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks (D4.5),
- 3) in discussion papers on the political economy of trade regimes (D.4.3), and
- 4) in our analyses on the policy coherence for sustainable development (D4.2).

This incremental approach will allow to further enrich outreach to key stakeholders involved, and the participation of a diversity of views in MATS outreach activities on transition pathways (WP5).

Project partners will continue to monitor reports and decisions of the different European institutions, and the role of relevant international institutions and processes, both governmental and non-governmental. These including the United Nations organizations such as Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) UN Environment Programme (UNEP), UN High Level Political Forum HLPF on Sustainable Development, UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), World Trade Organization (WTO), and the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). In addition, development in the African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCTA), Regional Economic Communities (REC), in the EU Free Trade Agreements (FTAs), Economic Partnership Agreements (EPA) and Association Agreements are useful to be followed.

Using the most effective dissemination activities and forms

The core instrument in MATS for connecting the project with relevant decision-makers, stakeholders and initiatives is the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub (WP6, T6.2). The scope of the interactive platform is two-fold: to act as a centralised knowledge hub for the different stakeholders' target audiences (see p. 5) interested in the project work; and to facilitate engagement and interaction throughout the projects' lifetime (via event pages, blogs...)

Regarding its function as a data and knowledge repository, the interactive platform is the central provider of information in the project's engagement activities. Its audience will evolve according to the engagement activities described above. It is a repository of information and knowledge stemming from the execution of the project's work. All material will be made available (except those restricted by data disclosure see WP7 and WP8) in a format allowing users to have a quick overview of the different MATS deliverables and to delve further into the detailed data, analysis, and related discussions.

Regularly updated news, especially from the 15 case studies, is provided – including through suitable social media communication channels such as Twitter and LinkedIn. Linkages to external data sources have been made available in the Trade Hub allowing stakeholders to link up with other relevant data sources, articles, policy documents, expert panels' reports, and CSOs' materials. The platform will eventually incorporate different types of data, including documents and reports, tabular data, statistical and analytical data, as well as geospatial data. As a one-stop-shop it will be linked to relevant external data sources and sites such as:

- Trade databases, such as the Trade Map of the International Trade Centre, World Bank's World Integrated Trade Solution, and the UN International Trade Database.
- Databases that comprise data from surveys and activities of international and national authorities, such as FAOSTAT and Eurostat.
- Information on agri-food trade regimes such as the WTO, practices, and impacts from national authorities such as the EU, and NGOs approached during the project.

The project has already produced outputs that are being shared more widely to our stakeholders and used as background material to engage into new discussions and engagement. However, the design of the deliverables still needs to be adapted to reach larger audiences, through:

- i. **Informative Discussion Briefs** highlighting the main conclusions and policy suggestions or outcomes for *relevant deliverables* in an accessible form hosted on the Sustainable Trade Hub. *See format in annex 2.*
- ii. **Adapted dissemination, participation, and feedback activities.** The Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub is being designed as the main platform for the presentation of MATS deliverables and data. The material repositied in the Trade Hub is backed by other support activities, including social media, webinars, and videos – and most importantly, supporting engagement into active discussions with MATS stakeholders and participation in their events.

The Trade Hub is designed for a user-friendly navigation with exhaustive search, link and data visualisation features. An interactive visual dashboard (main page) has been integrated, to allow the visitor to find the newest activities and compact but informative policy briefs at a fist glance.

Monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities

Key performance indicators for dissemination and exploitation activities

The progress of the dissemination and exploitation activities is monitored and evaluated on a six-monthly basis by the WP6, and project management teams based on a set of KPIs (key performance indicators) (see Table 4). The effectiveness of the engagement strategy, activities and tools will be assessed based on this monitoring, and any barriers identified. If necessary, specific elements of the engagement strategy (as described in this document) will be adjusted, and the activities and tools refined to ensure an effective engagement of the different stakeholders.

Deadlines, activities and tools for dissemination and exploitation		Key Performance indicators
	Final version of Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy created by M10	1
First target group	Number of registered users in the Platform user database by M12	150
	Total number of entries in the Interactive Modelling Toolbox by M24	20-30
	Number of case studies workshops by M24	20-30
	Number of backcasting and transition pathways workshops by M30	5
	Number of Policy Briefs (in English) by M24	5
	Number of Policy Briefs translated in FR, DE, IT, ES, NL and PL by M28	3
	Number of Sustainable Trade Webinar in MATS YouTube channel by M30	5
	Number of articles in specialist policy media by M30	10
	Number of participants in the high-level policy dialogue by M 42	80
Second target group	Peer-reviewed articles in international scientific journals by M 42	8
Third target group	Number of case study reports and fact sheets online by M30	15
	Number of articles, essays, posts in stakeholder journals by M 42	20

Table 4. Key Performance Indicators for dissemination and exploitation activities and tools.

Core indicators for the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub

All major project outputs are made available on the project's Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub, which is aimed at remaining available beyond the lifetime of MATS as part of a forthcoming business plan (with feedback from relevant actors and stakeholders). This Hub includes presentations, recorded webinars, and publications, as well as case study abstracts, fact sheets, discussion briefs, policy briefs and blogs.

Specific monitoring indicators for engagement will be linked to the Trade Hub, to assess its visibility and impact for the targeted groups. Table 5 summarises the core indicators to be monitored.

Indicator ID	Description	Target
STH1	Number of monthly users	700
STH2	Number of returning users	400
STH3	Monthly pageviews	2400
STH4	Monthly sessions	800
STH5	Average visit duration	2 min
STH6	Number of countries visiting	15

Table 5. Core indicators for the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub

The aforementioned indicators will be monitored via the relevant Monitoring and Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) features integrated in the website, along will possibly more detailed parameters like navigation patterns, search patterns; scenario usage (scenario's built, parameters used); downloads; interactive engagement (number of registrations, comments left, participants in discussion/community fora). The relevant consent forms will be designed, and users will be informed on the usage of the collected data where applicable. In any case, MATS data handling will be in full compliance with GDPR and broader data regulation directives in the EC (see WP7 and WP8). The monitoring and analysis of the aforementioned factors will also contribute to the formulation of a business plan for the Hub, to be developed collaboratively by the responsible technical partner (SCiO), the MATS coordinator and the partners primarily responsible for content creation. Indicative directions could be the establishment of a tiered subscription model, the provision of analytical functions over the data available in the Hub, and the provision of consulting and tutoring services. This will be further clarified depending on the directions to be adopted for expanding content and the ways project outcomes further mature and are positioned in the broader community.

Annexes

Annex 1. Complete List of Consortium Partners

-
 University of Helsinki (UH), Department of Economics and Management, Finland (project coordinator).
-
 KnowlEdge Srl (KE), Italy.
-
 Southern and Eastern Africa Trade Information and Negotiations Institute (SEATINI), Uganda.
-
 Research Centre on Animal Production, C.R.P.A. SPA, Department of Economics and Engineering (CRPA), Italy.
-
 SCiO – Big Data Analytics in Food Systems (SCiO), Greece.
-
 Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Spain.
-
 Transnational Institute (TNI), The Netherlands.
-
 The Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF), Tanzania.
-
 Oxfam Solidarité - Oxfam Solidariteit (OSOL), Belgium.
-
 Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI (FRAUNHOFER), Germany.
-
 Geoponiko Panepistimion Athinon (AUA), Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, Greece.
-
 North-West University (NWU), TRADE Research Focus Area, South Africa.
-
 Universität Bern (UBERN), World Trade Institute, Switzerland.
-
 Maastricht University (UM), Faculty of Law, The Netherlands.

Annex 2 Format for informative discussion briefs

DISCUSSION BRIEFS X/2021

TITLE 1st ROW

SUBTITLE 1st ROW

Funded by
the European Union

Introduction

Short description of the aim of the research question

Max: 2 para

Text here //

Highlights

Main highlights and conclusions of the research

(aim is to focus on the relevance to MATS objective: identify key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of trade on sustainable development and human rights.)

Max: 2 pages

Use of graphics, illustrations, highlights in box texts, ...

Text here //

Discussion points

Including: Limitations and assumptions/discussion points/evidence gaps/controversies and identify ways to address these

(aim is to identify relevant research and policy questions that can feed into the further research agenda and stakeholders-policy dialogue)

Max: 1 page

Text here //

For more information

Link to website and MATS research document

Link to request for more information about MATS/leave a message or reaction

Authors:

Annex 3. List of stakeholders for engagement and interaction

Below is a table of actors, of which some are stakeholders, organised per target group. We indicated for each actor if we intent to create engagement with our materials or go beyond and ensure real interaction. Target group III is not specifically taken up in this table as these are reached out directly en masse (for example through social media posts or newspaper articles) or indirectly through actors and stakeholders belonging to group I and II (for example sharing of webinar invites or MATS materials with consumers or farmers).

Table 6. List of stakeholders for engagement and interaction

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	Oxfam Uganda	CSO	Group I	Interaction
	Belgian Government	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Uganda Coffee Development Authority	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Ministry of Investment, Industry and Trade (MIIT), Tanzania	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Ministry of agriculture, Tanzania	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Sokoine University of Agriculture	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Tanzania Horticultural Association (TAHA)	Private sector	Group I	Interaction

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	Agricultural Non-State Actors Forum (ANSAF)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group I	Interaction
	Government of Tanzania	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	UCT Graduate School of Business	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), United Nations	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	World Research Institute	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Finland	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (MTK)	Farmer organisation	Group I	Interaction
	Natural Resources Institute, Finland (LUKE)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Ruralia Institute, University of Helsinki	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Consorzio Formaggio Parmigiano Reggiano	Private sector	Group I	Interaction
	Regione Emilia Romagna	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Consiglio per la ricerca e l'analisi dell'economia agraria (CREA)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Consorzio Prosciutto di Parma	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction
	Committee on Agriculture, Animal	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	industries and fisheries committee, Parliament of Uganda			
	Tourism, Trade, and Industry committee, Parliament of Uganda	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Committee on Agriculture, Tourism and Natural resources, EALA	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Coordinator on Food and Environmental Security	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Africa Biodiversity Network (ABN)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Alliance for Food Sovereignty Association (AFSA)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Trade Network Africa (TNA)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Rural Extension Agency of Maranhão State, Brazil	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Fundación de Apoyo a la Investigación en el Corredor Norte de Exportación (FAPCEN-Balsas)	Farmer organization	Group I	Interaction
	Fondo Mundial para la Naturaleza (WWF Brasil)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Brazilian Association of Vegetable Oil Industries	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction
	TradeHub	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Universität Bern	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	WTO Secretariat	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Le Réseau des Organisations de la Société Civile pour le Développement du Tonkpi – ROSCIDET	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Bioland (Sales)	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction
	DACHSER Food Logistics	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction
	Grüne Jugend Karlsruhe	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Institute of Systems Sciences, Innovation and Sustainability Research	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	University of Hohenheim International Agricultural Trade and Food Security	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Climate Farmers	Farmer organization	Group I	Interaction
	The Sustainability Initiative of South Africa NPC (SIZA)	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction
	CSAAWU - The Commercial, Stevedoring, Agricultural and Allied Workers Union	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	FAWU - Food and Allied Workers Union	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Union of Santorini Cooperatives, SantoWines	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction
	Hellenic Organization of Agricultural Insurances	Political/public institution	Group I	Interaction
	Stylis Olive Producers Cooperative	Private sector organization	Group I	Interaction

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	WWF Hellas	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Harokopio University / Dept. of Economics & Sustainable Development	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Hellenic Association of Agricultural Economists (ETAGRO)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Center for Renewable Energy Sources & Saving; Biomass Dept.	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Action Network for a Just Transition in the MENA Region (RÉSEAU-TANMO)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	University of Carthage, Tunisia	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Interaction
	Tunisian Platform for Alternatives	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	S2B - European Just Trade Coalition	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Friends of the Earth Europe	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Handel Anders	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Tunisian Observatory of Economy (OTE)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Siyada, North African Network for Food Sovereignty	Farmer organization	Group I	Interaction
	APESS(Association Pour la Promotion d'Élevage au Sahel et en Savane)	Farmer organization	Group I	Interaction
	CORET (Confederation Traditional Stockbreeder	Farmer organization	Group I	Interaction

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	Organisation in Africa)			
	Oxfam Nigeria	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Interaction
	Gret Burkina Faso	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	Roppa (Réseau des Organisations Paysannes et des Producteurs Agricoles de l'Afrique de L'Ouest)	Farmer organization	Group I	Interaction
	European Economic and Social Committee	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Campagne Mon Lait est Local	Civil Society Organisation	Group I	Engagement
	Comité Français pour la Solidarité Internationale (CFSI)	Civil Society Organisation	Group I	Engagement
	Groupe de Recherches et d'Echanges Technologiques (GRET)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	Center Cooperation International In Agricultural Research Development (CIRAD)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	Finnish Food and Drink Industries' Federation (ETL)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Raisio Group	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Raisio plc's Research Foundation	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Fazer Mills	Private sector	Group I	Engagement

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	Helsinki Mills Ltd	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Myllyn Paras	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Vaasan Ltd	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	O'LOVE	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	65 oats / Kinnusen Mylly Oy	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Gold&Green	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Polar Glucan	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Avena Nordic Grain Oy (Apetit Plc)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Hankkija	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	The Cereal Committee (VYR)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Lantmännen Oats	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Tate & Lyle Sweden Ab	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	AXA Swedish Harvest	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Oatly AB	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Swedish Oat Fiber	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Union of Santorini Cooperatives, SantoWines	Farmer Organization	Group I	Engagement
	Triodos Bank	Private Sector	Group I	Engagement
	International Institute for Sustainable Development	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Engagement
	World Trade Institute	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	European Seed Association	Private Sector	Group I	Engagement
	Institute for European Environmental Policy	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Engagement

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	Stylis Olive Producers Cooperative	Farmer Organization	Group I	Engagement
	South African Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development (DALRRD)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Western Cape Department of Agriculture	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Wines of South Africa (WOSA)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Engagement
	Vinpro	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Wine and Agricultural Ethical Trade Association (WIETA)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Engagement
	Fairtrade Africa	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Engagement
	SA Wine Industry Transformation Unit (SAWITU)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	ELGA SA	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	UN WFP	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Agriconsulting Europe	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	European Parliament	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	SEI – Stockholm Environment Institute	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	UNEP	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	IFPRI	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	IMF	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	UNDP	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	FEWS NET	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Global Nutrition Cluster	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Italian ministry of health	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	ASSICA	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Ministry of Industries and Trade (MIT)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Ministry of Works and Transport (MWT)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Ministry of Communication and Information Technology (MCIT)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries (MLF)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Chamber of Commerce, Industry and Agriculture (TCCIA)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Private Sector Foundation (TPSF)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Confederation of Tanzania Industries (CTI)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Horticultural Association (TAHA)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
	Agricultural Non State Actors Forum (ANSAF)	Civil Society Organization	Group I	Engagement
	Southern Agricultural Growth Corridor of Tanzania (SAGCOT)	Private sector	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Mercantile Exchange (TMX)	Private Sector	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Trade Development Authority (TANTRADE)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Cooperative Development Commission (TCDC)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	TradeMark East Africa	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	World Food Program (WFP)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (AGRA)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Agricultural Research Institute (TARI)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	University of Dar es Salaam (USDM)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	Tanzania Pesticide Research Institute (TPRI)	Academics/ Scientific organizations	Group II	Engagement
	Tanzania Cotton Board (TCB)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Sisal Board (TSB)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tea Board of Tanzania (TBT)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Bureau of Standards (TBS)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement
	Tanzania Ports Authority (TPA)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement

Name of contact person(s)	Organisation	Type of Organisation (political institution, farmer organisation, CSO, academics, or private sector)	Group I or II.	Expected engagement or interaction
[REDACTED]	Tanzania Airports Authority (TAA)	Political/public institution	Group I	Engagement